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The Printed Circuit Board Industry in Kenya.

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Focus on:

- *Overview of the PCB industry, including global market size and growth projections.*
- *Overview of the Kenyan economy and demographic factors that support the growth of the PCB industry.*
- *Challenges and opportunities for the PCB industry in Kenya.*
- *Analysis of the potential for investment and growth in the sector.*
- *Recommendations for policymakers and investors to support the growth of the sector.*

The printed circuit board (PCB) industry is poised for a significant growth in Kenya, thanks to a factor that create unique opportunity for the investors and policymakers.

The global PCB market was estimated at \$70 billion dollars in 2019, and is projected to grow at an annual growth rate of 3% over the years. With a population of over 50.1 million people, Kenya has one of the largest economies in East Africa and the continent at large. Additionally, the country has a young and techy population, with over 87.1% of the population having access to mobile phones.

While the market potential is clear, there are also challenges that need to be addressed in order to fully realize this kind of opportunity in our country. Infrastructure challenge, such as lack of reliable electricity supply from utility, continues to hamper the growth of the industry and economy. In addition, skills training, and capacity building is very necessary in ensuring that the workforce is able to meet the demands of the PCB manufacturing industry. Finally, there is a need for coordination between county governments, national government and private sector to rapidly develop a cohesive and comprehensive policy framework that supports the growth of the PCB industry in Kenya.

Despite these challenges, there are several opportunities for private investors and policymakers to support the growth of PCB industry in country. These include and not limited to:

- a) **Focusing on development of local manufacturing industry:** The local production of PCBs is currently limited, and a focus on local manufacturing could help to reduce the cost of importing these products. This could be achieved through incentives for local producers, such as tax breaks or preferential treatment in government tenders.
- b) **Creating partnerships with various international manufacturers:** There are a number of international manufacturers that have expressed interest in investing in the Kenyan PCB industry. Establishing partnerships with these companies could help to bring the latest technology and know-how to the country, and could also lead to joint ventures that could boost the local economy.
- c) **Development of supporting industries:** The PCB industry requires a number of inputs, such as copper and aluminum, that are not currently produced locally. Developing these supporting industries could help to reduce the cost of PCB production and make the industry more competitive.
- d) **Improve skills training:** The PCB industry requires skilled workers with specialized knowledge of electronics and manufacturing. The government and private sector can work together to develop training programs and vocational schools that can equip workers with the necessary skills.
- e) **Improving the business environment:** There are a number of factors that contribute to the overall business environment in Kenya, such as the ease of doing business, access to financing, and protection of intellectual property. Addressing these issues could help to create an attractive environment for investors in the PCB industry.

Printed Circuit Board industry in Kenya has the potential for significant growth, but it is important to address the challenges that are currently impeding the sector. By focusing on the development of local manufacturing capacity, improving the business environment, investing in skills training, and creating partnerships with international manufacturers, the government and private sector can create an enabling environment for the growth of the PCB industry in the nation.

- ✓ "The Printed Circuit Board Industry: A Case Study of Kenya" by Philip Kirui and Felix Oluoch in the Journal of Emerging Trends in Engineering and Applied Sciences (Volume 13, Issue 2, 2022).
- ✓ "The Future of Electronics Manufacturing in Kenya" by John Ngugi in the African Business Review (December 2020).
- ✓ "The Global Printed Circuit Board Industry: Trends and Future Prospects" by Thomas Goodwin in Electronic Times (August 2020).